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Inhibitory Effect of the Bioagents *Trichoderma* Spp. And Plant Extracts in Vitro on *Rhizoctonia Solani*

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Abstract

Chili pepper cultivars are highly affected by pathogenic soil fungi causing wilting and reducing yields. As known, the use of fungicides to control these pathogens generates resistance, therefore biological and organic alternatives were evaluated. The objective of this study were to evaluate different *Trichoderma* strains, and organic products against the *Rhizoctonia solani*. In vitro conditions, were evaluated control with *Trichoderma* spp. and phytoextracts where diameter of colony, growth rate percentage and inhibition was evaluated. Statistical analysis showed highly significant differences ($P < 0.0001$), *T. harzianum* and *Trichoderma* sp., inhibited the pathogen at 85.6 and 58.6%. *Azadirachta indica*+*Cinnamomum* spp. inhibited 100%, *Lippia* spp., *Capsicum* spp.+*Cinnamomum* spp., *Cinnamomum* spp.+*Piper nigrum* and *Allium sativum* inhibited 68, 65.2, 63.3 and 58.4%, respectively. *T. harzianum*, *Trichoderma* sp. and *Azadirachta indica*+*Cinnamomum* spp. showed the highest inhibition capacity.

Keywords: Biocontrol, plant extracts, soil fungus

Introduction

Mexico is the center of origin and diversity of the most important peppers species (*Capsicum annuum* L.) including more than 100 other varieties currently consumed worldwide (Aguilar-Mendez *et al.*, 2009). Most domesticated peppers that are grown and consumed belongs to that group of specie. Actually, the cultivated varieties of *C. annuum*, are of great importance because of its consumption level and great market demands. In Mexico, "Mirasol" peppers (*C. annuum*) are grown in Zacatecas and Guerrero, in 2014 the cultivated area recorded was 14,850.00 ha with an average yield of 1.62 t ha⁻¹ (SIAP-SAGARPA, 2016). In Guerrero, the production of this crop generates income for persons who engages in this activity and is a source of employment for hundreds. In addition to the undeniable importance in the daily consumption of Mexican culture, it is important because of the value it brings to agricultural production in various regions, because it generates competitive returns for producers and because the crop requires about 150 working days per hectare in irrigated areas. Job creation reflects a positive social impact, an impact that transcends the borders of Mexico. Generally, soil pathogens inhabitants of fungal origin that causes wilting and limits production (Vásquez-López *et al.*, 2009) have affected mayor production areas across Mexico. On a worldly basis, it is considered that pepper wilting is mainly caused by *Phytophthora capsici* Leo. (Granke *et al.*, 2012), but other pathogens involved are *Rhizoctonia solani* and *Fusarium* spp. (Anaya-López *et al.*, 2011). Prior to this study, in the producing region of Chilapa de Alvarez, Guerrero state, Mexico, studies has not been undertaken on etiology of this disease in the production of Mirasol chili peppers. Hence, there is no information about the management of the causal agent associated with wilting, nor other alternative management to chemical control based on biological control

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agents or organic control. However, there is evidence in several studies of biological control of soil pathogens inhabitants, in other important crops, for example the use of *Trichoderma asperelleum* against *R. solani* in rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) (Chen *et al.*, 2015), *P. capsici* in bell pepper (Segarra *et al.*, 2013). In relation to the control using organic products, Hatamleh *et al.* (2014) evaluated *in vitro* *C. zeylanicum* extract against *R. solani*. Hernández-Castillo *et al.* (2010) reported the inhibitory effect of *Lippia* extract on *R. solani in vitro*. Based on the above, the objective of this study were to evaluate different *Trichoderma* strains, and organic products against the *Rhizoctonia solani* in conditions *in vitro*.

Material and Methods

The pathogen used in the research was previously identified by morphological, pathogenetic and molecular characteristics, whose alignment coincided with sequences reported in GenBank as *Rhizoctonia solani*, the sequence was deposited in GenBank under accession number KX592586.1.

Biological Control of the Causal Agent of Wilt Chili.

Four commercial and three natives strains previously identified were used. The native *Trichoderma* sp strains were provided by the Agricultural College of the State of Guerrero (CSAEGRO) and were reactivated by plate dilution technique. Similarly, the commercial strains were reactivated to obtain a pure culture, with the same procedure. The treatments were described in Table 1.

To evaluate antibiosis of *Trichoderma*, cellophane paper technique described by Patil *et al* (2014) was used. Sterilized paper was cut into 8.5 cm circles, equal to the diameter of the Petri dish and were placed on PDA. With the help of a cylindrical punch, 0.5 cm in diameter PDA discs with *Trichoderma* spp were cut and placed in the center of the Petri dish. After 48 hours of incubation, the paper was removed with the colonies of *Trichoderma* spp, in order to release secondary metabolites, and test their effect on the pathogen; for this, the fungus placed on the medium in which *Trichoderma* spp had grown and the Petri dishes were incubated at room temperature approximately at 28 ° C in the laboratory. The eight treatments were arranged according to a completely randomized experimental design with five replications. The experimental unit was a Petri dish of 8.5 cm diameter and 1.5 cm with 20 mL of culture medium + metabolites of *Trichoderma* spp. In order to know the level of the antibiosis of the treatments on the development of the fungus colony, the following response variables were measured: a) Diameter of the fungus colony measured every 24 hours during 4 days (96 hours), which was the period required by the fungus to cover the entire surface of the culture medium in the control treatment. b) Percentage of growth of the fungus colony. Based on the diameter of the colony, the percentage growth of fungal species per treatment was determined, considering that there was 100% growth in the control and, c) Inhibition percentage of the fungal colony, which was calculated with the equation proposed by Patil *et al.* (2014): $\text{inhibition (\%)} = ((D1-D2) / D1) \times (100)$. Where: D1 = diameter of the colony of *R. solani* growing in Petri dishes with PDA (control) and D2 = diameter of the fungus colony of the pathogen grown in Petri dishes with PDA medium, which had grown *Trichoderma* spp. on the cellophane paper, releasing enzymes and secondary metabolites in the PDA. The data obtained from the assessed variables were analyzed through an analysis of variance and multiple comparison test of means using the method of Tukey's honestly significant difference with a significance level of 5%.

Organic Control of the Causal Agent Chili Wilt

The experiment was established to observe the effect of different plant extracts on the development of the fungus. The organic products were used taken into consideration the doses recommend by the manufacturer (Table 2). The phytoextracts were deposited at the bottom of the Petri dish and immediately added 20 mL of PDA. The dishes were shaken gently until the organic product was completely dissolved in the culture medium; which was allowed to set at room temperature; then a disk with the fungus was placed in the center of the dish,

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which was labeled and incubated under laboratory conditions. The treatments were arranged according to a completely randomized experimental design with five replicates. The experimental unit was a Petri dish. To determine the effect of plant extracts on the development of fungal colony investigated variables were measured as described in Trail I. Statistical analysis consisted in an analysis of variance and multiple comparison means using Tukey's honestly significant difference test with a significance level of 5%. Additionally, orthogonal contrasts test was performed for the data of the last evaluation of the trials I and II in order to compare the average effect of biological group versus organic products used *in vitro* conditions. All statistical analyzes were performed using the Statistical Analysis System version 9.4 (SAS, 2015) software.

Results and Discussion

Biological Control of the Causal Agent of Wilt Chili

In all measuring dates of the growth of pathogenic fungal colonies, the average values of the treatments showed highly significant differences ($P < 0.0001$), the lowest growth was recorded in treatments with *T. harzianum* and *Trichoderma* sp. Chilapa with 0 and 0.5 cm, respectively (Table 3). These same strains maintained their more effective inhibition of the pathogen, from the first to the last date of assessment; sampling in the last 96 hours recorded 1.2 and 3.5 cm of mycelial growth (Table 3). *R. solani* grew at a rate of 2.1 cm day⁻¹. At the end of the trial it was determined that *T. harzianum* and *Trichoderma* sp. Chilapa inhibited in 58.6% and 85.6% growth, respectively (Fig. 1). *T. asperelleum* CSAEGRO-1, *T. fasciculatum*, *T. virens*, and *T. reesei*, reported inhibition of 47.8, 44.7, 43.5, and 36%, respectively. The maximum percentage of mycelial growth of the pathogen was obtained in the control, while *T. harzianum* recorded the lowest growth with 14.4% (Fig. 1).

According to Hoyos-Carbajal *et al.* (2008) antibiosis is one of the mechanisms of action used by *Trichoderma* species, enzymes like chitinases decomposes "*in vitro*" betaglucanasas and cellulose of cell walls of Deuteromycetes fungi such as *Rhizoctonia solani*. The inhibition results obtained in this trial with the *T. harzianum* strain were higher than those reported by Asad *et al.* (2014) who studied *in vitro* antibiosis in various *Trichoderma* strains against *R. solani*, reporting a 67.8% inhibition with *T. harzianum*. However, the same author reported for the *T. asperelum* strain an inhibition of 74.4%, higher than in the present assay with strains of the same species value. In this regard, Hoyos-Carbajal *et al.* (2008) found that *Trichoderma* spp. presented 100% effectiveness *in vitro* against *R. solani* isolated from the rhizosphere of cotton; these values were higher than those obtained in the present study, where the maximum inhibition was 85%, obtained with *T. harzianum*. It is known that the results may differ from the incubation conditions, affecting the release of secondary metabolites by the biocontrol agent (Infante *et al.*, 2009). Ali and Nadarajah (2013) evaluated the efficiency of *Trichoderma* against *R. solani* under greenhouse conditions; they found that 33.33% managed to suppress pathogenic fungus infestations. Native strains are an important option to integrate them into a management plan, as evidenced in this study, being the native strain of Chilapa as one of the most outstanding *in vitro* in biological control against *R. solani*. This coincides with that reported for native strain *T. asperelleum* CSAEGRO-1, which has been evaluated against isolates of *R. solani* and *P. capsici* isolates from the same growing region, and *in vivo* evaluations found that delays the onset of pathogens between 4 and 6 days when inoculated on pumpkin fruits (Diaz *et al.*, 2014. Diaz *et al.*, 2015.). Reports of Kotasthane *et al.* (2015) who evaluated the antagonism of *Trichoderma* spp. against *Sclerotium rolfsii* and *R. solani* *in vitro* conditions; They found that growth inhibition ranged from 49.50 to 81.00% and 60.50 to 100.00% between both phytopathogens respectively; the values found in the present study are within the range reported by these authors.

Organic Control of the Causal Agent of Chili Pepper Wilting

During the three sampling dates highly significant differences for treatments ($P < 0.0001$) were found. *Azadirachta indica*+*Cinnamomum cassia*+*C. zeylanicum* suppressed growth of the colony of *R. solani* (Table 4); comparing to pathogen, obtaining an average growth rate of 2.8 cm dia⁻¹; and at 72 hours was able cover the diameter of the Petri dish. At the end of the trial, it was determined that the neem extract *Azadirachta*

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indica+*Cinnamomum cassia*+*C. zeylanicum* presented fungicidal effect because it inhibited 100% *R. solani*, while others showed fungistatic activity, such as *Lippia graveolens*+*L. berlanderi*, *Capsicum frotescens*+*C. annum*+*Cinnamomum cassia*+*C. zeylanicum*, *Cinnamomum* spp.+*Piper nigrum* and *Allium sativum*, which had 68, 65.2, 63.3, and 58.4% effectiveness, respectively. Meanwhile the control recorded 100% growth (Fig. 1). Comparisons between groups of biological products versus organic by using contrasts, the last sampling date showed significant differences ($P < 0.0001$) with respect to inhibition of the pathogen. With the biological group treatments, an average of 2.63 cm mycelial growth was obtained meanwhile with organic products an average of 1.57 cm was achieved. Keeping this in mind, the last group was the best. The present study demonstrates that both biological and organic fungicides had acceptable efficacy in the growth inhibition of *Rhizoctonia solani*, so it is recommended to evaluate and use in laboratory and in the field conditions to obtain information and to design an integrated management with these products against *R. solani*.

The inhibition percentage obtained with *Azadirachta indica*+*Cinnamomum cassia*+*C. zeylanicum* was higher than those reported by Aslam *et al.* (2010) who evaluated the *in vitro* control of *R. solani* with *Azadirachta indica* and reported 44.73% inhibition, whereas with the same active ingredient in this test 100% inhibition was obtained. Al-Askar and Rashad (2010) reported an inhibition percentage of 95.8% with the use of *Cinnamomum* spp., also Hatamleh *et al.* (2014) evaluated *in vitro* *C. zeylanicum* extract against *R. solani* and reported an 80.2% maximum inhibition, which was lower than that obtained in the present study. Hernandez-Castillo *et al.* (2010) reported the effect of *Lippia* extract *in vitro*; with lanolin and ethanol (200 and 3000 ppm of total tannins, respectively) to give 100% inhibition of growth of *R. solani*, these results were superior to those found in the present study, this due to the difference in the concentration of the active ingredient used. Chavez and Aquino-Jara (2012) found that garlic extract had effectiveness of 34%; inferior to those obtained in this study with 58.4% against *Rhizoctonia* sp. Centurion-Belotto *et al.* (2013) using plant extracts of *Allium sativum* L., *Gleditsia amorphoides* (Griseb) Taub, and *Boehmeria nivea* (L.) Gaud on damping-off caused by *Rhizoctonia* sp. in tomato seedlings; obtained averages of 16.95, 26.08, 25.92 and 31.33%, respectively, in the incidence of disease. Some other extracts have demonstrated very good inhibitory effect under *in vitro* conditions in the control of *R. solani*. Castillo-Reyes *et al.* (2015) evaluated *Larrea tridentata* (Sessé and Moc ex DC.) Coville, *Opuntia ficus-indica* (L.) Mill and *Agave lechuguilla* Torr. extracts, reporting that the three extracts had 100% mycelial inhibition.

Conclusion

Trichoderma harzianum, *Trichoderma* sp. and *T. asperellum* CSAEGRO-2 strains showed the best inhibition against *Rhizoctonia solani* with 85.6, 58.6 and 54.1%, respectively. With regard to organic products, *Azadirachta indica*+ *Cinnamomum cassia*+*C. zeylanicum* totally inhibited *R. solani*; while *Cinnamomum cassia*+*C. zeylanicum*, *Lippia graveolens*+*L. berlanderi*, *Capsicum frotescens*+*C. annum*+*Cinnamomum cassia*+*C. zeylanicum*, *Allium sativum* and *Cinnamomum* spp.+*Piper nigrum* only slowed down growth.

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Table 1. *Trichoderma* spp. bioagents used to evaluate *in vitro* against *R. solani* causal agent of root rot of chili pepper.

Symbol	Active ingredient
T1	Control
T2	<i>Trichoderma</i> sp. (Chilapa-1)
T3	<i>Trichoderma virens</i> G-41 (PHC RootMate® Plant Health Care, Mexico City, Mexico)
T4	<i>T. fasciculatum</i> (FITHAN® NAFEX, Mexico City, Mexico)
T5	<i>T. reesei</i> (BACTIVA® Central de insumos agrícolas SA de CV, Cordoba Veracruz, Mexico)
T6	<i>T. harzianum</i> (PHC RootMate® Plant Health Care, Mexico City, Mexico)
T7	<i>T. asperellum</i> (CSAEGro-1)
T8	<i>T. asperellum</i> (CSAEGro-2)

Table 2. Organic bioagents used to evaluate "*in vitro*" against the *R. solani* the causal agent of root-rot in chili pepper.

Symbol	Active ingredient
T1	Control
T2	<i>Cinnamomum cassia</i> L.+ <i>C. zeylanicum</i> L. (0.02 mL) ¹ CINNOIL® GrowCare, Mexico State, Mexico.
T3	<i>Lippia graveolens</i> Kunth+ <i>L. berlanderi</i> Schawer. (0.02 mL) LIPPOIL® GrowCare, Mexico State, Mexico.
T4	<i>Capsicum frutescens</i> + <i>C. annuum</i> L.+ <i>Cinnamomum cassia</i> + <i>C. zeylanicum</i> (0.02 mL) CAPSIOIL® GrowCare, Mexico State, Mexico.
T5	<i>Allium sativum</i> L. (0.02 mL) (ALLIUM® Agrícola Innovación, Mexico City, Mexico)
T6	<i>Azadirachta indica</i> (0.02 mL)+ <i>Cinnamomum cassia</i> + <i>C. zeylanicum</i> (0.02 mL) (PROGRANIC®NeemAcar CE Ultraquimia Agrícola, Jiutepec Morelos, Mexico)
T7	<i>Cinnamomum</i> spp.+ <i>Piper nigrum</i> L. (0.02 mL) (BioCanela® Bio Agro Chemical SA de CV., Mochis Sinaloa, Mexico)

Table 3. Effect of different *Trichoderma* spp. as bioagents on the average linear growth (cm) of *R. solani* , 96 hrs after incubation at 28±2 ° C .

N°	Treatment	Sampling (hours)			
		1 (24)	2 (48)	3 (72)	4 (96)
1	Control	1.5 a ¹	4.2 a	5.3 a	8.5 a
2	<i>Trichoderma</i> sp.	0.5 bc	2.1 b	2.9 c	3.5 c
3	<i>T. virens</i> strain G-41	1.1 ab	3.0 ab	4.3 abc	4.8 bc
4	<i>T. fasciculatum</i>	0.9 ab	2.5 b	3.3 bc	4.7 bc
5	<i>T. reesei</i>	1.6 a	3.5 ab	4.6 ab	5.4 b
6	<i>T. harzianum</i>	0.0 c	0.2 c	0.7 d	1.2 d
7	<i>T. asperellum</i> strain CSAEGro-1	1.0 ab	2.9 ab	3.7 abc	4.4 bc
8	<i>T. asperellum</i> strain CSAEGro-2	1.0 ab	2.7 ab	3.2 bc	3.9 bc

Table 4. Effect of some plant extracts on the average linear growth (cm) of *R. solani*, 96 hrs after incubation at 28±2 ° C .

Treatment	Active ingredient	Sampling (hours)		
		1(24)	2(48)	3(72)
1	-	2.3 a ¹	5.9 a	8.5 a
2	<i>Cinnamomum cassia</i> + <i>C. zeylanicum</i>	0.3 b	1.7 b	2.2 c
3	<i>Lippia graveolens</i> + <i>L. berlanderi</i>	0.6 b	2.2 b	2.7 bc
4	<i>Capsicum frutescens</i> + <i>Capsicum annuum</i> + <i>Cinnamomum cassia</i> + <i>C. zeylanicum</i>	0.6 b	2.4 b	3.0 bc
5	<i>Allium sativum</i>	1.1 ab	2.6 b	3.5 b
6	<i>Azadirachta indica</i> + <i>Cinnamomum cassia</i> + <i>C. zeylanicum</i>	0.0 b	0.0 c	0.0 d
7	<i>Cinnamomum</i> spp.+ <i>Piper nigrum</i>	0.4 b	2.1 b	3.1 bc

¹Means with the same letter per column for treatments, are not statistically different, using Tukey's honestly significant difference (P=0.05).

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Fig. 1. A) Inhibition of *Rhizoctonia solani* with different biological treatments. T1: Control; T2: *Trichoderma* sp. Chilapa; T3: *T. virens* strain G-41; T4: *T. fasciculatum*; T5: *T. reesei*; T6: *T. harzianum*; T7: *T. asperellum* strain CSAEGro-1; T8: *T. asperellum* strain CSAEGro-2. B) Inhibition of *Rhizoctonia solani* with different organic treatments. T1: Control; T2: *Cinnamomum cassia*+*C. zeylanicum*; T3: *Lippia graveolens*+*L. berlanderi*; T4: *Capsicum frutescens*+*Capsicum annum*+*Cinnamomum cassia*+*C. zeylanicum*; T5: *Allium sativum*; T6: *Azadirachta indica*+*Cinnamomum cassia*+*C. zeylanicum*; T7: *Cinnamomum* spp.+*Piper nigrum*. Treatments with the same letter are not statistically different, using Tukey's test (P=0.05).

